

FUZZY LOGIC-BASED PRE-OPERATIVE RISK ANALYSIS: A MATLAB APPROACH

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Abstract

Pre-operative risk assessment is extremely crucial to be performed before every surgical procedure, as it enables health care providers to prevent and limit any complications and risks that the patient might encounter during or after the procedure. This assessment traditionally involves different kinds of examinations and evaluations, including physical examinations, disease-specific assessments, Metabolic Equivalent of Task (MET) scores, ASA scores, etc., eventually helping in designing personalized pre-surgical, surgical, and post-surgical plans, as well as risk mitigation plans. Existing fuzzy models and systems helping in pre-operative risk assessment, including the Physiological and Operative Severity Score for the enumeration of Mortality and Morbidity (POSSUM) and American Society of Anesthesiologists Physical Status Classification System (ASA) scores, are either procedure-specific (e.g., esophageal cancer prognosis, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, etc.) or too complex or subjective, respectively. Considering this, we developed a Fuzzy Logic-based pre-operative risk assessment system which could be used for a variety of different surgeries, using variables common to the majority of surgeries that happen all over the world which include age, blood pressure, comorbidities, procedure's complexity, and hemoglobin levels were the five parameters we used as inputs for our fuzzy-logic-based system, and each fuzzy set including that of the output variable (risk), was represented using triangular or trapezoidal membership functions, ensuring smooth transitions between categories using 18 set of clinically sound rules. This approach offers a reliable tool for clinicians to identify high-risk patients and adjust surgical plans accordingly, ultimately enhancing patient safety and optimizing healthcare delivery.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Pre-operative risk stratification is vital to be performed before every surgery, since it helps the healthcare professionals analyze every patient's health condition, their underlying conditions if any, and eventually helps them plan and strategize the patient's surgery,

necessary precautionary measures to avoid intraoperative medical emergencies, and post-surgery care, in order to avoid any intra or post-operative medical emergencies which might occur bringing life threatening situations. There have been several cases reported where the pre-operative risk assessment

declared a low risk score, however, due to the assessment being not extensive enough, there were intra-operative medical emergencies reported, which could have been life threatening too if would not have been managed promptly with efficiency. The table below shows some reported cases, and the importance of extensive, and appropriate pre-operative risk assessment.

A few clinical reports have stressed the value of thorough preoperative risk stratification. For example, there was a report of an unexpected intra-operative cardiac arrest in a non-cardiac surgery that had been initially regarded as low risk [1]. In another case series, patients with unsuspected obstructive sleep apnea presented with serious respiratory and cardiac consequences, resulting in disastrous intraoperative outcomes [2]. Also, perioperative anaphylaxis has been reported as a cause of life-threatening collapses where allergies or risk factors were not known prior to the operation [3,4]. Such cases highlight the utmost importance of comprehensive and accurate preoperative assessment to reduce unexpected complications. To resolve such issues, medical professionals utilize various preoperative risk assessment strategies. The American Society of Anesthesiologists Physical Status (ASA-PS) grading is extensively used as a rapid risk indicator for audit and triage [5,6]. The Metabolic Equivalent of Task (MET) score measures the level of physical effort which can be tolerated by a patient and thus gives an indication of surgical fitness [7]. The Duke Activity Status Index (DASI) is yet another measure that estimates self-reported functional capacity [8], whereas the Revised Cardiac Risk Index (RCRI) is used to determine preoperative cardiac risk and direct testing and perioperative management strategies [9]. Taken together, these methods demonstrate the heterogeneous approaches that are used in practice, but also the limitations that drive the creation of substitute models like those based on fuzzy logic.

Regardless to these techniques existing, and being widely used by healthcare professionals for determining pre-operative risk of patients in order to minimize intra-operative medical emergencies, there still are some limitations observed. For example, if we talk about the ASA-PS classification, then it is subjective, and demonstrates only moderate inter-rater reliability [10]. Coming towards RCRI, it shows

weak calibration and reduced discrimination in patients possessing high surgical risk, or vascular surgical patients [11]. The issue raised regarding POSSUM and P-POSSUM is that it often shows high discrimination, but really weak calibration [12]. And lastly, the DASI questionnaire often overestimates functional capacity, in comparison to objective measures in patients who are about to undergo a cancer-related surgery [13]. Considering these flaws, the concept of using fuzzy logic based systems for assisting healthcare professionals with pre-operative risk assessment landed. A study revealed, that fuzzy based systems, can very efficiently handle clinical uncertainty, and also support critical care decision-making process, eventually explaining why fuzzy logic-based systems are a good fit for pre-operative risk assessment [14]. Another study showed the reliability of a fuzzy model in stratifying pre-anesthetic risk, which also targets the potential of such systems in the healthcare industry, however still showing room for broader external validation [15]. Like so, there are several other researches publically available too, where the fuzzy logic-based systems were developed and tested to see how useful they could be for pre-operative risk assessment including a fuzzy hybrid multi-criteria model in order to assess and rank risks in organ transplant based surgeries [16], a pre-anesthetic fuzzy model, developed using 270 rules, and 10 inputs domains (BMI, age, smoking, diabetes, cardiac and a few more), especially designed for laparoscopic cholecystectomy patients [15]. But regardless to all these existing pre-operative risk assessment fuzzy models, we still developed our own because our fuzzy model is designed with an aim to be flexible and generalized to most types of surgeries, rather than being specific to a particular type of surgery like a few existing ones [15, 17, 18, 16].

1.2: Study objective

The objective of this research is to develop a preoperative risk assessment system based on fuzzy logic and compare it with the commonly applied ASA classification in order to increase reliability and minimize subjectivity in surgical risk assessment.

2. Methodology

This study used a fuzzy logic-based approach to assess preoperative risk in surgical patients. Starting from the choice of Input parameters, clinically relevant

input variables were chosen by reviewing the literature and using expert clinical judgment. The final parameters included age, comorbidities, procedure complexity, hemoglobin concentration, and blood pressure. These factors are known to affect perioperative outcomes and were selected as inputs for the fuzzy inference system. A Mamdani-type fuzzy inference system (FIS) was created using MATLAB.

Membership functions were defined for each input variable, covering ranges typically seen in clinical settings. The system produced one output variable, Risk Level, which was categorized into four groups: Low, Moderate, High, and Critical. This structure allowed for a clear and meaningful assessment of patient risk which is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 General structure of the proposed fuzzy system for preoperative risk management

Eighteen fuzzy if-then rules were developed, based on clinical knowledge and existing literature on preoperative risk assessment. These rules created logical links between combinations of input variables and their associated risk levels shown in figure 2, some of the examples of rules are provided below;

- IF Comorbidities IS Severe AND Procedure Complexity IS Moderate THEN Risk Level IS Critical.
- IF Comorbidities IS Severe AND Blood Pressure IS Critical THEN Risk Level IS Critical.
- IF Comorbidities IS Severe AND Hemoglobin IS Low THEN Risk Level IS Critical.

Fig 2-Fuzzy interface

IF Comorbidities IS Moderate AND Age IS Elderly THEN Risk Level IS High
 IF Procedure Complexity IS High AND Age IS Elderly THEN Risk Level IS High
 IF Comorbidities IS None AND Procedure Complexity IS Low AND Hemoglobin IS High AND

Blood Pressure IS Normal AND Age IS Young THEN Risk Level IS Low

The fuzzy system was executed using the MATLAB Fuzzy Logic Toolbox, which was integrated with the Simulink environment. MATLAB scripts supported static analysis, including rule evaluation and surface visualization, while Simulink offered a dynamic framework for testing patient datasets.

Fig 3-Preoperative risk assesment fuzzy system using Simulink

Model validation was carried out in two phases. In the first phase, literature-based validation was performed using a set of ten representative patient cases drawn from published studies. The fuzzy system outputs were compared with results obtained from Simulink simulations, demonstrating close agreement with only slight numerical differences [19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. In the second phase, clinical dataset validation was conducted on a cohort of 100 patients. The results of the fuzzy logic system were compared against the established American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) scoring system, showing strong alignment with 70% raw agreement. Together, these two validation phases confirmed the reliability and clinical

applicability of the fuzzy system for preoperative risk assessment.

3.Results

In order to validate the risk prediction of our fuzzy model, we also Integrated the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox Model with Simulink and then we tested the realistic patient data in our system both of the systems i.e.; fuzzy and Simulink.

3.1 Fuzzy vs Simulink Outputs

The following table 1 presents the patient data used for preoperative risk assessment, showing input variables, fuzzy and Simulink outputs, calculated risk levels, and relevant case references;

Table 1 Output of fuzzy VS Simulink

Patient ID	Age	Comorbidities	Procedure complexity	Hemoglo bin	B.p	Fuzzy output	Simulink output	Risk value
P001	60	High	High	13.5	145 /90	0.41	0.409	Moderate
P002	70	Moderate	Moderate	12.5	160 /95	0.72	0.716	High
P003	55	Moderate	Moderate	12	190	0.84	0.835	High
P004	65	High	High	11.5	210	0.82	0.822	High
P005	72	Moderate	High	11	130 /85	0.46	0.455	Moderate
P006	80	High	High	9.5	145 /90	0.82	0.822	High
P007	75	Moderate	Moderate	12	135 /80	0.54	0.5357	Moderate
P008	82	High	High	10.5	140 /85	0.85	0.849	High
P009	60	Low	Moderate	14	120 /80	0.36	0.355	Low
P010	68	High	High	10	145 /90	0.82	0.822	High

Figure 4-Comparison of Fuzzy Logic output and Simulink output for preoperative risk assessment across patients. The graph shows close agreement between both methods, with annotated risk levels (Low, Moderate, High) for each patient

Figure 4 shows the comparison of fuzzy logic output to Simulink output shows a strong consistency, with

only slight numerical differences noted. Both approaches accurately categorized patients into their

corresponding risk levels (Low, Moderate, High), confirming the precision and dependability of the fuzzy logic-based preoperative risk evaluation system.

3.2 Patient Distribution:

A total of 100 patients underwent evaluation utilizing both the fuzzy logic-based risk assessment system and the traditional ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) scoring system. According to the ASA scoring, patients were grouped into categories

from ASA I (a healthy individual) to ASA II (an individual with mild systemic issues), ASA III (an individual with severe systemic issues), and ASA IV (an individual with severe systemic issues that poses a continual threat to life) shown in fig 5. Through the fuzzy logic system, patients were categorized into four groups: Low, Moderate, High, and Critical demonstrated in figure 6.

Patient Distribution by ASA Score

Figure 5: The distribution of patients across categories in both systems is presented in ASA category.

Patient Distribution by Fuzzy Category

Figure 6- The distribution of patients across categories in both systems is presented in Fuzzy category.

3.3 Alignment Between ASA and Fuzzy Scoring:

Out of 100 patients, 70 patients (70%) were classified into the same risk category by both systems (figure 7). The fuzzy logic-based scoring system shows strong general correspondence with the ASA classification with a concordance rate of 70%. This result is consistent with the expected trend that has the higher ASA scores associated with higher risks and is in total concordance for the ASA I and ASA III groups. There were minor misclassifications: ASA II cases were

classified into neighboring classes (ASA I and III), while ASA IV patients were overestimated as ASA III to some extent. However, these inconsistencies occur between neighboring categories, something common in clinical risk assessment systems. Overall, the findings suggest that the system can serve as a useful adjunctive tool for the evaluation of preoperative risks.

Figure 7- shows a stacked bar chart of ASA scores versus fuzzy categories, demonstrating that patients with higher ASA scores were predominantly classified into higher fuzzy risk levels

4. Conclusion

Preoperative risk assessment continues to be a foundation stone for surgical safety, allowing clinicians to predict complications and personalize perioperative care to the patient. Established systems like the ASA Physical Status classification are useful but restricted by subjectivity and inter-rater variation. A fuzzy logic-based risk assessment system was created in this study and evaluated against literature-derived case and a clinical database of 100 patients. The findings indicated good correlation with the ASA system with 70% raw concordance. The fuzzy model had flawless concordance with ASA I and ASA III, small misclassification within ASA II, and an underestimation of ASA IV patients as ASA III. These differences only arose between successive categories, as might be expected in clinical risk scoring. Together, these results demonstrate the potential of fuzzy logic to act as an effective and versatile support tool for preoperative assessment that can minimize

subjectivity, manage uncertainty, and facilitate decision-making in surgical planning.

5. Limitations

This study has certain limitations, such as the fact that it only includes five input parameters (age, hemoglobin, blood pressure, comorbidities, and procedure complexity). However, there is still a chance that our model will incorporate many more input domains that are common to the majority of surgeries performed worldwide, which would ultimately improve the accuracy and dependability of our pre-operative risk assessment system. Furthermore, as the input domain of this system expands, so does the number of rules, which makes our approach more practical for predicting risk given any kind of input values. Therefore, we think this system has great potential to become a revolutionary pre-operative risk assessment tool, which would not only be easy for healthcare professionals to learn and

use, but also an efficient, fast and trust worthy tool for this purpose.

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